

The Future Energy Market Model (FEM): A Mathematical Description

David Holmer^{*1,2} and Ali Darudi^{1,3}

¹ZHAW School of Management and Law, Center for Energy and Environment,
Gertrudstrasse 8, 8400 Winterthur, Switzerland

²University of Basel, Faculty of Business and Economics, Peter Merian-Weg 6, 4002 Basel,
Switzerland

³ETHZ, Energy Science Center (ESC), Sonneggstrasse 28, SOI C 1, 8006 Zürich,
Switzerland

November 18, 2025
Model version: 1.0.0

Abstract

This document provides a comprehensive mathematical formulation of the Future Energy Market (FEM) model, a multi-period, multi-scenario energy system optimization model for coupled electricity and district heating systems. The model is formulated as a linear program that minimizes total system costs including investment and operational expenditures, while ensuring energy balance, technical constraints, fuel limitations, etc. The model incorporates detailed representations of generation technologies including renewables, conventional thermal plants, and combined heat and power; storage systems such as batteries, pumped hydro, heat storages, fossil methane and hydrogen; demand-side flexibility from electric vehicles, heat pumps, and demand-side response; as well as transmission networks. This documentation focuses on the essential mathematical structure and is designed to be accessible to energy system modelers and researchers.

Contents

1	Introduction	4
1.1	Overview	4
1.2	Model Scope and Applications	4
1.3	Model History and Development	4
1.4	License	4
1.5	Software Availability	4
1.6	Model Data and Approach	5
2	Mathematical Formulation	5
2.1	Model Structure and Notation	5
2.1.1	Notation Convention	5
2.1.2	Stochastic Programming Structure	5
2.2	Set Definitions	5

*Corresponding author: david.holmer@zhaw.ch

2.3	Parameters	6
2.4	Decision Variables	8
2.5	Objective Function	9
2.5.1	Electricity Side Investment Costs	9
2.5.2	Electricity Side Operation Costs	10
2.5.3	Lost Load Costs	10
2.5.4	Slack Costs (disabled by default)	10
2.5.5	District Heating Investment Costs	10
2.5.6	District Heating Operation Costs	10
2.5.7	Fuel Storage Investment Costs	10
2.5.8	Thermal Curtailment Penalty	10
2.6	Energy Balance Constraints	11
2.6.1	Electricity Energy Balance	11
2.6.2	District Heating Energy Balance	11
2.6.3	Storage Balance Constraints	11
2.6.4	Generation and Capacity Constraints	11
2.7	Investment Limit Constraints	12
2.7.1	Generation Capacity Investment Limits	12
2.7.2	Energy Capacity Investment Limits	12
2.7.3	Thermal Generation Capacity Investment Limits	12
2.7.4	Thermal Energy Capacity Investment Limits	13
2.8	Energy Production Limit Constraints	13
2.8.1	Total Energy Production Limit	13
2.8.2	Storage Fuel Limit	13
2.9	Transmission Line Constraints	13
2.10	Lost Load Constraints	13
2.11	District Heating Technology Constraints	13
2.11.1	Resistive Heater	13
2.11.2	Heat Pump (District Heating)	13
2.11.3	Combined Heat and Power (CHP)	13
2.12	Fuel Tracking and Limitation Constraints	14
2.12.1	Fuel Consumption Tracking (Electric Plants)	14
2.12.2	Fuel Consumption Tracking (DH Plants)	14
2.12.3	Total Fuel Consumption	14
2.12.4	Annual Fuel Limit	14
2.12.5	Fuel Storage Investment Limit	14
2.13	Demand Side Response (DSR) Constraints	14
2.13.1	Daily Energy Shift Limit	14
2.13.2	Daily Energy Balance	15
2.14	Electric Vehicle (EV) Constraints	15
2.14.1	Weekly EV Energy Consumption	15
2.14.2	Hourly EV Charging Rate	15
2.15	Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) Constraints	15
2.15.1	V2G Charging Rate	15
2.15.2	V2G Discharging Rate	15
2.16	Building Heat Pump Flexibility Constraints	15
2.16.1	Building Thermal Storage Balance	15
2.16.2	Thermal Storage Limits	15
2.16.3	Weekly Average Temperature	16
2.16.4	Maximum Heating Capacity	16
2.17	District Heating DSR Constraints	16

2.17.1	Thermal Energy Deviation Tracking	16
2.17.2	Deviation Limits	16
2.17.3	Weekly Start/End Conditions	16
2.17.4	Weekly Average Temperature	16
2.17.5	Inflexible Demand Share	16
2.18	Additional Technology-Specific Constraints	17
2.18.1	PTES Storage-to-Charge Ratio Constraint	17
2.18.2	DH Pump Capacity Constraint	17
2.18.3	RES Generation Fixing Constraint	17
3	Model Characteristics	17
3.1	Model Type	17
3.2	Temporal Resolution	17
3.3	Spatial Coverage	17
3.4	Technology Coverage	18
4	Conclusion	18
5	Acknowledgments	18

1 Introduction

1.1 Overview

This document describes a multi-period, multi-scenario energy system optimization model for electricity and district heating systems. The model minimizes total system costs (investment and operation) while ensuring energy balance, technical constraints, and fuel limitations.

1.2 Model Scope and Applications

The FEM model is designed to analyze long-term energy system planning questions, including:

- Optimal investment in generation and storage capacity
- Integration of variable renewable energy sources
- Coupling of electricity and district heating sectors
- Role of flexibility options (storage, demand-side response, sector coupling)
- Multi-scenario robust planning under uncertainty
- Sensitivity analysis of transmission capacity assumptions
- Impact of fuel availability constraints

1.3 Model History and Development

The FEM model builds on the Swissmod electricity market model [6]. A previous version of the FEM model focused primarily on the electricity sector [2]. The current version has been enhanced with the addition of the district heating sector, various sector coupling technologies, and additional flexibility options.

1.4 License

The FEM model is open-source software licensed under the GNU General Public License v3.0 (GNU GPLv3). This allows users to freely use, modify, and distribute the model, provided that any derivative works are also licensed under the same terms. For more details, see <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.html>.

1.5 Software Availability

This document describes features and assumptions of the FEM model corresponding to the public release **v1.0.0** of the software. The code for the model is publicly available at the following locations:

- Release (v1.0.0): https://github.com/DerDavidZHAW/FEM_public/tree/v1.0.0
- General repository (main): https://github.com/DerDavidZHAW/FEM_public/tree/main

Users should cite the specific release tag (v1.0.0) when referencing the model implementation described in this document.

How to Cite

If you use this model or its description, please cite as follows:

Holmer, D., & Darudi, A. (2025). The Future Energy Market Model (FEM): A Mathematical Description (v1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17722336>

1.6 Model Data and Approach

The FEM model operates mainly with data from the Ten-Year Network Development Plan 2022 (TYNDP22) [3] for European electricity system characteristics and the Swiss Energy Perspectives 2050+ [7] for Switzerland-specific energy system data.

The model can be configured for target years 2035 and 2050, which determines the installed capacities of various technologies, demand levels, and other system characteristics. For weather-dependent inputs (renewable generation profiles, temperature-dependent demands), the model uses historical weather data from the years 1995, 2008, and 2009, which can be used to represent different climate conditions and variability.

The FEM model employs different modeling approaches for the electricity and district heating sectors:

- **Electricity sector (brownfield):** The model includes existing generation capacity as fixed infeed (represented by \mathcal{T}^{inf}) that is available without requiring investment decisions. Additional capacity can be invested in through the optimization.
- **District heating sector (greenfield):** Most of the thermal generation and storage capacity must be determined through investment decisions by the optimization model, representing a complete system build-out.

2 Mathematical Formulation

2.1 Model Structure and Notation

2.1.1 Notation Convention

For clarity and readability, this document uses simplified mathematical notation. When constraints are defined for a specific node n (or week w , day d , etc.), summations over plants or transmission lines are implicitly restricted to those located at or connected to that node. For example, $\sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{gen}} g_{p,t,s}$ in the energy balance constraint for node n represents the sum over all generating plants at node n . The full implementation includes explicit spatial and temporal mapping sets, but these are omitted here to focus on the essential model structure.

2.1.2 Stochastic Programming Structure

This model follows a two-stage stochastic programming framework:

- **First-stage decisions (here-and-now):** Investment variables ($\bar{g}_p, \bar{e}_p, \bar{ch}_p, \bar{g}_p^{DH}, \bar{e}_p^{DH}, \bar{ch}_p^{DH}, \bar{e}_f^{fuel}$) are made before uncertainty is revealed and are therefore independent of scenarios. These represent strategic capacity expansion decisions.
- **Second-stage decisions (wait-and-see):** Operational variables ($g_{p,t,s}, ch_{p,t,s}, soc_{p,t,s}$, etc.) are indexed by scenario s and represent operational decisions made after observing the realized scenario (demand, renewable availability, fuel prices, etc.).

Note on implementation: In the Python/Pyomo implementation, investment variables are technically indexed by scenario, but explicit constraints enforce their equality across all scenarios. This mathematical description adopts the more intuitive scenario-independent notation to emphasize their role as first-stage decisions in the stochastic program.

2.2 Set Definitions

Set	Description
\mathcal{T}	Time steps (hours) in the model
\mathcal{D}	Days in the model
\mathcal{W}	Weeks in the model
\mathcal{N}	Electricity nodes (regions)
\mathcal{N}^{DH}	District heating nodes
\mathcal{L}	Transmission lines (NTC interconnections)
\mathcal{L}^{imp}	Transmission lines for import to a node
\mathcal{L}^{exp}	Transmission lines for export from a node
\mathcal{P}	All plants (including DH plants connected to electric grid)
\mathcal{P}^{gen}	Plants that can generate electricity
$\mathcal{P}^{storage}$	Storage plants (batteries, pumped hydro, etc.)
$\mathcal{P}^{storage,noSOC}$	Liquid fuel storage plants (no state-of-charge dynamics)
\mathcal{P}^{pump}	Plants that can pump/charge (not only hydro anymore)
\mathcal{P}^{equal}	Storage plants with equal charge/discharge capacity
\mathcal{P}^{v2g}	Vehicle-to-grid capable EVs (one aggregated V2G plant representing all V2G capacity)
\mathcal{P}^{dsr}	Demand-side response assets (one plant per node representing all DSR at that node)
\mathcal{P}^{RES}	Renewable energy source plants
\mathcal{P}^{inv}	Plants that can be invested in
$\mathcal{P}^{fuel,lim}$	Plants with limited fuel availability in CH
$\mathcal{P}^{energymax}$	Plants with energy capacity limits
$\mathcal{P}^{energylim}$	Plants with total energy production limits
\mathcal{P}^{DH}	District heating plants
$\mathcal{P}^{DH,storage}$	DH storage plants (same as $\mathcal{P}^{DH,TES}$)
$\mathcal{P}^{DH,res}$	Resistive heating plants
$\mathcal{P}^{DH,hp}$	Heat pump plants (DH)
$\mathcal{P}^{DH,TES}$	Thermal energy storage plants
$\mathcal{P}^{DH,CHP}$	CHP plants in district heating
$\mathcal{P}^{DH,dsr}$	Demand-side response in DH (one plant per DH node representing all thermal DSR at that node)
$\mathcal{P}^{DH,fuelLim}$	DH plants with fuel limits
$\mathcal{P}^{DH,inv}$	DH plants that can be invested in
$\mathcal{P}^{DH,cost,th}$	DH plants with costs on thermal side only
\mathcal{T}^{inf}	Infeed technologies (existing capacity without investment requirements)
$\mathcal{T}^{demand,inflex}$	Inflexible demand technologies
\mathcal{F}^{lim}	Fuels with limited availability
\mathcal{BA}	Building archetypes
\mathcal{M}_p^{fuel}	Mapping: Fuel type of plant p
\mathcal{M}_d^t	Mapping: Set of time steps in day d
\mathcal{M}_w^t	Mapping: Set of time steps in week w
\mathcal{M}_t^w	Mapping: Week corresponding to time step t
\mathcal{S}	Scenarios
\mathcal{LL}	Lost load cost steps

2.3 Parameters

Parameter	Description
$C_{p,s}^{op,slp}$	Operation cost slope for plant p in scenario s [CHF/MWh]
$C_{p,s}^{op,qdr}$	Operation cost quadratic coefficient for plant p in scenario s [CHF/MWh ²]
$C_p^{inv,gen}$	Investment cost for generation capacity for plant p [CHF/MW]
$C_p^{inv,e}$	Investment cost for energy capacity for plant p [CHF/MWh]
$C_p^{inv,discharge}$	Investment cost for discharge capacity for plant p [CHF/MW]
$C_f^{inv,fuel}$	Investment cost for fuel f storage [CHF/MWh]
$C_{k,s}^{lostload}$	Cost of lost load for cost step $k \in \mathcal{LL}$ in scenario s [CHF/MWh]
w_s	Weight of scenario s in objective function [-]
$D_{n,tech,t,s}$	Demand of node n for technology $tech$ at time t in scenario s [MWh]
$D_{n,t,s}^{DH}$	District heating demand at node n at time t in scenario s [MWh]
$I_{n,tech,t,s}$	Infeed from technology $tech$ to node n at time t in scenario s [MWh]
$I_{n,s}^{KVA}$	Infeed from waste incineration at DH node n in scenario s [MWh]
$\eta_{p,s}^{in}$	Charging efficiency of storage plant p in scenario s [-]
$\eta_{p,s}^{out}$	Discharging efficiency of storage plant p in scenario s [-]
$\eta_{p,s}^{gen}$	Generation efficiency of plant p in scenario s for fuel tracking [-]
$\eta_{p,s}^{DH}$	Efficiency of DH plant p in scenario s (resistive, heat pump) [-]
$\rho_{p,s}^{CHP}$	Power-to-heat ratio of CHP plant p in scenario s [-]
$SOC_{p,s}^{init}$	Initial state of charge for storage plant p in scenario s [-]
δ_p^{TES}	Decay rate for thermal energy storage plant p [-]
$A_{p,t,s}$	Availability factor of plant p at time t in scenario s [-]
$F_{p,t,s}^{in}$	Inflow to storage plant p at time t in scenario s [MWh]
$F_{p,t,s}^{out}$	Outflow from storage plant p at time t in scenario s [MWh]
\overline{G}_p	Maximum generation capacity limit for plant p [MW]
\overline{E}_p	Maximum energy capacity limit for plant p [MWh]
\overline{G}_p^{DH}	Maximum thermal generation capacity limit for plant p [MW _{th}]
\overline{E}_p^{DH}	Maximum thermal energy capacity limit for plant p [MWh _{th}]
$\overline{E}_{p,s}^{total}$	Total energy production limit for plant p in scenario s [MWh]
$\overline{LL}_{k,s}$	Lost load capacity for cost step $k \in \mathcal{LL}$ in scenario s [MWh]

Parameter	Description
$\overline{DSR}_{p,s}^{DH}$	Maximum deviation for demand-side response for DH DSR at node/region $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,dsr}$ in scenario s [MWh _{th}]
$\overline{NTC}_{l,t,s}^{exp}$	Export limit on line l at time t in scenario s [MWh]
$\overline{NTC}_{l,t,s}^{imp}$	Import limit on line l at time t in scenario s [MWh]
$\overline{F}_{f,s}^{import}$	Annual fuel import capacity for fuel f in scenario s [MWh]
$\overline{F}_{f,s}^{prod,CH}$	Annual fuel production capacity in CH for fuel f in scenario s [MWh]
$\overline{F}_{f,s}^{storage,inv}$	Maximum fuel storage investment capacity for fuel f in scenario s [MWh]
$\overline{P}_{t,s}^{EV,charge}$	EV charging power rate at time t in scenario s [MW]
$E_{w,s}^{EV}$	Weekly EV electricity consumption for week w in scenario s [MWh]
$\overline{P}_{p,t,s}^{V2G,charge}$	V2G charging power rate at time t in scenario s [MW]
$E_{p,s}^{V2G}$	V2G battery capacity in scenario s [MWh]
$Q_{ba,t,s}$	Thermal consumption of building archetype ba at time t in scenario s [MWh _{th}]
$COP_{ba,t,s}$	Coefficient of performance of heat pump for building archetype ba at time t in scenario s [-]
$\overline{Q}_{ba,s}$	Maximum heating capacity for building archetype ba in scenario s [MW]
$\overline{TH}_{ba,s}^+$	Positive thermal storage limit for building archetype ba in scenario s [MWh _{th}]
$\overline{TH}_{ba,s}^-$	Negative thermal storage limit for building archetype ba in scenario s [MWh _{th}]
$r_{storage/charge}$	Storage to charge ratio for PTES (e.g., 168 hours) [-]
α_{flex}	Share of households that heat flexibly [-]
β_{dsr}^{shift}	Daily energy shift limit factor for DSR [-]

2.4 Decision Variables

Variable	Description
$g_{p,t,s}$	Generation (discharge) from plant p at time t in scenario s [MWh]
$soc_{p,t,s}$	State of charge of storage plant p at time t in scenario s [MWh]
$ch_{p,t,s}$	Charging (pumping) of storage plant p at time t in scenario s [MWh]
$LL_{n,t,k,s}$	Lost load for node n at time t for cost step $k \in \mathcal{LL}$ in scenario s [MWh]
$curt_{n,t,s}$	Curtailment of RES at node n at time t in scenario s [MWh]
$spill_{p,t,s}$	Spilled water from hydro plant p at time t in scenario s [MWh]
$Ex_{l,t,s}$	Export on transmission line l at time t in scenario s (+ export, - import) [MWh]

Variable	Description
$g_{p,t,s}^{DH}$	Thermal generation from DH plant p at time t in scenario s [MWh _{th}]
$ch_{p,t,s}^{DH}$	Thermal charging of DH storage plant p at time t in scenario s [MWh _{th}]
$soc_{p,t,s}^{DH}$	Thermal state of charge of TES plant p at time t in scenario s [MWh _{th}]
$curt_{n,t,s}^{DH}$	Thermal curtailment at DH node n at time t in scenario s [MWh _{th}]
$dev_{p,t,s}^{DSR,DH}$	Thermal energy deviation for DH DSR at node/region $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,dsr}$ at time t in scenario s [MWh _{th}]
\bar{g}_p	Invested generation capacity for plant p [MW]
\bar{ch}_p	Invested pumping/charging capacity for plant p [MW]
\bar{e}_p	Invested energy storage capacity for plant p [MWh]
\bar{g}_p^{DH}	Invested thermal generation capacity for plant p [MW _{th}]
\bar{ch}_p^{DH}	Invested thermal pumping capacity for plant p [MW _{th}]
\bar{e}_p^{DH}	Invested thermal energy capacity for plant p [MWh _{th}]
\bar{e}_f^{fuel}	Invested fuel storage capacity for fuel f [MWh]
$FC_{p,t,s}^{plant}$	Fuel consumption of plant p at time t in scenario s [MWh _{fuel}]
$FC_{f,t,s}^{fuel}$	Total fuel consumption of fuel type f at time t in scenario s [MWh _{fuel}]
$th_{ba,t,s}$	Thermal storage level of building archetype ba at time t in scenario s [MWh _{th}]
$slack_{p,t,s}^{SOC,+}$	Positive slack for SOC constraint for plant p at time t in scenario s [MWh]
$slack_{p,t,s}^{SOC,-}$	Negative slack for SOC constraint for plant p at time t in scenario s [MWh]

2.5 Objective Function

The model minimizes the total system costs across all scenarios:

$$\min C^{inv,el} + C^{inv,DH} + C^{inv,fuel} + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \left(C_s^{op,el} + C_s^{lostload} + C_s^{slack} + C_s^{op,DH} \right) + C^{curt,DH,penalty} \quad (1)$$

where the cost components are defined as follows:

2.5.1 Electricity Side Investment Costs

$$\begin{aligned} C^{inv,el} = & \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{inv}} \left(c_p^{inv,gen} \cdot \bar{g}_p + \frac{c_p^{inv,gen}}{10^6} \cdot \bar{g}_p^2 \right) \\ & + \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{energymax} \cap \mathcal{P}^{inv}} c_p^{inv,e} \cdot \bar{e}_p \\ & + \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{v2g}} c_p^{inv,discharge} \cdot \bar{ch}_p \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Note: Hydrogen plants have a separate discharge capacity investment. The quadratic term has been added for performance reasons during the solving process. To not alter the results, it is multiplied with a tiny factor.

2.5.2 Electricity Side Operation Costs

$$C_s^{op,el} = w_s \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{gen}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \left(c_{p,s}^{op,slp} \cdot g_{p,t,s} + c_{p,s}^{op,qdr} \cdot g_{p,t,s}^2 \right) + w_s \cdot 0.1 \cdot \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{fuel,lim} \cap \mathcal{P}^{pump}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} ch_{p,t,s} \quad (3)$$

2.5.3 Lost Load Costs

$$C_s^{lostload} = w_s \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{LL}} c_{k,s}^{lostload} \cdot LL_{n,t,k,s} \quad (4)$$

2.5.4 Slack Costs (disabled by default)

$$C_s^{slack} = w_s \cdot 10^6 \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{storage}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \left(slack_{p,t,s}^{SOC,+} + slack_{p,t,s}^{SOC,-} \right) \quad (5)$$

2.5.5 District Heating Investment Costs

$$C^{inv,DH} = \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,inv}} c_p^{inv,gen} \cdot \bar{g}_p^{DH} + \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,TES}} \left(c_p^{inv,gen} \cdot \bar{g}_p^{DH} + c_p^{inv,e} \cdot \bar{e}_p^{DH} \right) \quad (6)$$

2.5.6 District Heating Operation Costs

$$C_s^{op,DH} = w_s \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,cost,th}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} c_{p,s}^{op,slp} \cdot g_{p,t,s}^{DH} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathcal{P}^{DH,cost,th}$ are DH plants with costs exclusively on thermal side.

2.5.7 Fuel Storage Investment Costs

$$C^{inv,fuel} = \sum_{f \in \mathcal{F}^{lim}} c_f^{inv,fuel} \cdot \bar{e}_f^{fuel} \quad (8)$$

2.5.8 Thermal Curtailment Penalty

$$C^{curt,DH,penalty} = 1.1 \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}^{DH}} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} curt_{n,t,s}^{DH} \quad (9)$$

2.6 Energy Balance Constraints

2.6.1 Electricity Energy Balance

For each node $n \in \mathcal{N}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{gen}} g_{p,t,s} + \sum_{tech \in \mathcal{T}^{inf}} I_{n,tech,t,s} + \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}^{imp}} Ex_{l,t,s} \\
& + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{L}\mathcal{L}} LL_{n,t,k,s} \\
= & \sum_{tech \in \mathcal{T}^{demand,inflex}} D_{n,tech,t,s} + \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{pump}} ch_{p,t,s} \\
& + \sum_{l \in \mathcal{L}^{exp}} Ex_{l,t,s} + curt_{n,t,s}
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

2.6.2 District Heating Energy Balance

For each DH node $n \in \mathcal{N}^{DH}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH}} g_{p,t,s}^{DH} + I_{n,s}^{KVA} = D_{n,t,s}^{DH} + \sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,storage}} ch_{p,t,s}^{DH} + curt_{n,t,s}^{DH} \tag{11}$$

2.6.3 Storage Balance Constraints

Electricity Storage Balance For each storage plant $p \in \mathcal{P}^{storage}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}, t > 1$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
soc_{p,t,s} = & soc_{p,t-1,s} + \eta_{p,s}^{in} \cdot ch_{p,t,s} - \frac{g_{p,t,s}}{\eta_{p,s}^{out}} \\
& + F_{p,t,s}^{in} - F_{p,t,s}^{out} - spill_{p,t,s}
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Note: This constraint applies for all hours except the first hour ($t = 1$), which is handled by the storage initial condition constraint below. The inflows, outflows, and spilling terms are mostly only applicable for hydro plants.

Thermal Storage Balance For each TES plant $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,TES}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}, t > 1$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$soc_{p,t,s}^{DH} = (1 - \delta_p^{TES}) \cdot soc_{p,t-1,s}^{DH} + \eta_{p,s}^{in} \cdot ch_{p,t,s}^{DH} - \frac{g_{p,t,s}^{DH}}{\eta_{p,s}^{out}} \tag{13}$$

Note: This constraint applies for all hours except the first hour ($t = 1$), which is handled by the storage initial condition constraint below.

Storage Initial Condition For each storage plant $p \in \mathcal{P}^{storage}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$soc_{p,t=1,s} = SOC_{p,s}^{init} \cdot \bar{e}_p \quad (\text{equality for all except EVs, inequality } \leq \text{ for EVs}) \tag{14}$$

2.6.4 Generation and Capacity Constraints

Generation Limit For each plant $p \in \mathcal{P}^{gen}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$g_{p,t,s} \leq A_{p,t,s} \cdot \bar{g}_p \tag{15}$$

Thermal Generation Limit For each DH plant $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$g_{p,t,s}^{DH} \leq \bar{g}_p^{DH} \quad (16)$$

Charging Power Limit For each flexible plant $p \in \mathcal{P}^{pump}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$ch_{p,t,s} \leq A_{p,t,s} \cdot \bar{ch}_p \quad (17)$$

Thermal Charging Power Limit For each DH storage plant $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,storage}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$ch_{p,t,s}^{DH} \leq A_{p,t,s} \cdot \bar{ch}_p^{DH} \quad (18)$$

Equal Generation and Pumping Capacity For certain storage types (batteries, most pumped storage), $p \in \mathcal{P}^{equal}$:

$$\bar{ch}_p \leq \bar{g}_p \quad (19)$$

Exception: Hydrogen plants can have different electrolyzer and fuel cell capacities. Note: In most cases, only the generation capacity has an allocated cost in the objective function. I.e., the model will set the charging capacity equal to the generation capacity.

Storage Energy Limit For each storage plant $p \in \mathcal{P}^{storage}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$soc_{p,t,s} \leq \bar{e}_p \quad (20)$$

For V2G: $soc_{p,t,s} \leq E_{p,s}^{V2G}$ (fixed battery capacity)

Thermal Storage Energy Limit For each TES plant $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,TES}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$soc_{p,t,s}^{DH} \leq \bar{e}_p^{DH} \quad (21)$$

2.7 Investment Limit Constraints

2.7.1 Generation Capacity Investment Limits

For each investable plant $p \in \mathcal{P}^{inv}$:

$$\bar{g}_p \leq \bar{G}_p \quad (22)$$

2.7.2 Energy Capacity Investment Limits

For each investable plant $p \in \mathcal{P}^{inv} \cap \mathcal{P}^{energymax}$:

$$\bar{e}_p \leq \bar{E}_p \quad (23)$$

2.7.3 Thermal Generation Capacity Investment Limits

For each investable DH plant $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,inv}$:

$$\bar{g}_p^{DH} \leq \bar{G}_p^{DH} \quad (24)$$

2.7.4 Thermal Energy Capacity Investment Limits

For each investable TES $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH, TES} \cap \mathcal{P}^{DH, inv}$:

$$\bar{e}_p^{DH} \leq \bar{E}_p^{DH} \quad (25)$$

2.8 Energy Production Limit Constraints

2.8.1 Total Energy Production Limit

For energy-limited plants $p \in \mathcal{P}^{energylim}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} g_{p,t,s} \leq \bar{E}_{p,s}^{total} \quad (26)$$

2.8.2 Storage Fuel Limit

For liquid fuel storage plants $p \in \mathcal{P}^{storage, noSOC}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} g_{p,t,s} \leq \bar{e}_p \quad (27)$$

2.9 Transmission Line Constraints

For each line $l \in \mathcal{L}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$-\overline{NTC}_{l,t,s}^{imp} \leq Ex_{l,t,s} \leq \overline{NTC}_{l,t,s}^{exp} \quad (28)$$

Positive values indicate export from start node to end node; negative values indicate import.

2.10 Lost Load Constraints

For each node $n \in \mathcal{N}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, lost load cost step $k \in \mathcal{LL}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$LL_{n,t,k,s} \leq \overline{LL}_{k,s} \quad (29)$$

2.11 District Heating Technology Constraints

2.11.1 Resistive Heater

For $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH, res}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$g_{p,t,s}^{DH} = \eta_{p,s}^{DH} \cdot ch_{p,t,s} \quad (30)$$

2.11.2 Heat Pump (District Heating)

For $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH, hp}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$g_{p,t,s}^{DH} = \eta_{p,s}^{DH} \cdot ch_{p,t,s} \quad (31)$$

where $\eta_{p,s}^{DH}$ represents the COP.

2.11.3 Combined Heat and Power (CHP)

For $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH, CHP}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$g_{p,t,s}^{DH} = \frac{g_{p,t,s}}{\rho_{p,s}^{CHP}} \quad (32)$$

where $\rho_{p,s}^{CHP}$ is the power-to-heat ratio.

2.12 Fuel Tracking and Limitation Constraints

2.12.1 Fuel Consumption Tracking (Electric Plants)

For $p \in \mathcal{P}^{fuel,lim}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$FC_{p,t,s}^{plant} = \frac{g_{p,t,s}}{\eta_{p,s}^{gen}} \quad (33)$$

2.12.2 Fuel Consumption Tracking (DH Plants)

For $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,fuel,lim}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$FC_{p,t,s}^{plant} = \frac{g_{p,t,s}^{DH}}{\eta_{p,s}^{gen}} \quad (34)$$

2.12.3 Total Fuel Consumption

For each fuel $f \in \mathcal{F}^{lim}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$FC_{f,t,s}^{fuel} = \sum_{p: \mathcal{M}_p^{fuel}=f} FC_{p,t,s}^{plant} \quad (35)$$

2.12.4 Annual Fuel Limit

For each fuel $f \in \mathcal{F}^{lim}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} FC_{f,t,s}^{fuel} \leq \frac{|\mathcal{T}|}{8760} \left(\bar{F}_{f,s}^{import} + \bar{F}_{f,s}^{prod,CH} + \bar{e}_f^{fuel} \right) \quad (36)$$

Note: The factor $\frac{|\mathcal{T}|}{8760}$ scales the annual fuel limits proportionally when modeling periods shorter than a full year.

2.12.5 Fuel Storage Investment Limit

For each fuel $f \in \mathcal{F}^{lim}$:

$$\bar{e}_f^{fuel} \leq \bar{F}_{f,s}^{storage,inv} \quad (37)$$

2.13 Demand Side Response (DSR) Constraints

Note: Each element $p \in \mathcal{P}^{dsr}$ represents one aggregated DSR plant per node, capturing all demand-side response capacity at that node.

2.13.1 Daily Energy Shift Limit

For $p \in \mathcal{P}^{dsr}$, day $d \in \mathcal{D}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\sum_{t \in \mathcal{M}_d^t} (g_{p,t,s} + ch_{p,t,s}) \leq \beta_{dsr}^{shift} \cdot \bar{g}_p \quad (38)$$

The default for β_{dsr}^{shift} is 3.

2.13.2 Daily Energy Balance

For $p \in \mathcal{P}^{dsr}$, day $d \in \mathcal{D}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\sum_{t \in \mathcal{M}_d^t} g_{p,t,s} = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{M}_d^t} ch_{p,t,s} \quad (39)$$

2.14 Electric Vehicle (EV) Constraints

2.14.1 Weekly EV Energy Consumption

For each week $w \in \mathcal{W}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\sum_{t \in \mathcal{M}_w^t} ch_{EV_CH,t,s} = E_{w,s}^{EV} \quad (40)$$

2.14.2 Hourly EV Charging Rate

For each time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$ch_{EV_CH,t,s} \leq \bar{P}_{t,s}^{EV,charge} \quad (41)$$

2.15 Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) Constraints

Note: The set \mathcal{P}^{v2g} contains a single aggregated V2G plant representing all vehicle-to-grid capacity in the system.

For the V2G plant $p \in \mathcal{P}^{v2g}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

2.15.1 V2G Charging Rate

$$ch_{p,t,s} \leq \bar{P}_{p,t,s}^{V2G,charge} \quad (42)$$

2.15.2 V2G Discharging Rate

$$g_{p,t,s} \leq \bar{P}_{p,t,s}^{V2G,charge} \quad (43)$$

2.16 Building Heat Pump Flexibility Constraints

2.16.1 Building Thermal Storage Balance

For each building archetype $ba \in \mathcal{BA}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$th_{ba,t,s} = th_{ba,t-1,s} - Q_{ba,t,s} + COP_{ba,t,s} \cdot ch_{ba,t,s} \quad (44)$$

with boundary condition: $th_{ba,t=1,s} = 0$ and $th_{ba,t=|\mathcal{T}|,s} = 0$

2.16.2 Thermal Storage Limits

For each building archetype $ba \in \mathcal{BA}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\overline{TH}_{ba,s}^- \leq th_{ba,t,s} \leq \overline{TH}_{ba,s}^+ \quad (45)$$

2.16.3 Weekly Average Temperature

For each building archetype $ba \in \mathcal{BA}$, week $w \in \mathcal{W}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\sum_{t \in \mathcal{M}_w^t} th_{ba,t,s} = 0 \quad (46)$$

2.16.4 Maximum Heating Capacity

For each building archetype $ba \in \mathcal{BA}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$ch_{ba,t,s} \leq \bar{Q}_{ba,s} \quad (47)$$

2.17 District Heating DSR Constraints

Note: Each element $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,dsr}$ represents one aggregated DSR plant per DH node, capturing all thermal demand-side response capacity at that node.

2.17.1 Thermal Energy Deviation Tracking

For $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,dsr}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$dev_{p,t,s}^{DSR,DH} = \sum_{t' \in \mathcal{M}_t^w : t' \leq t} (ch_{p,t',s}^{DH} - g_{p,t',s}^{DH}) \quad (48)$$

where \mathcal{M}_t^w gives the week of time step t .

2.17.2 Deviation Limits

For $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,dsr}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$-\overline{DSR}_{p,s}^{DH} \leq dev_{p,t,s}^{DSR,DH} \leq \overline{DSR}_{p,s}^{DH} \quad (49)$$

2.17.3 Weekly Start/End Conditions

For $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,dsr}$, week $w \in \mathcal{W}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$dev_{p,t_{\text{first}}(w),s}^{DSR,DH} = 0 \quad (50)$$

$$dev_{p,t_{\text{last}}(w),s}^{DSR,DH} = 0 \quad (51)$$

2.17.4 Weekly Average Temperature

For $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH,dsr}$, week $w \in \mathcal{W}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\sum_{t \in \mathcal{M}_w^t} dev_{p,t,s}^{DSR,DH} = 0 \quad (52)$$

2.17.5 Inflexible Demand Share

For each DH node $n \in \mathcal{N}^{DH}$, time $t \in \mathcal{T}$, scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$:

$$\sum_{p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH} \setminus \mathcal{P}^{DH,dsr}} g_{p,t,s}^{DH} \geq (1 - \alpha_{flex}) \cdot D_{n,t,s}^{DH} \quad (53)$$

This ensures a minimum share of demand is met inflexibly because a certain amount of consumption is expected to remain inflexible.

2.18 Additional Technology-Specific Constraints

2.18.1 PTES Storage-to-Charge Ratio Constraint

For PTES (Pit Thermal Energy Storage) plants $p \in \mathcal{P}^{DH, TES}$ with tech type "PTES":

$$\bar{e}_p^{DH} \geq 24 \cdot r_{storage/charge} \cdot \bar{g}_p^{DH} \quad (54)$$

This enforces that PTES takes approximately at least one week (168 hours) to fill at full capacity.

2.18.2 DH Pump Capacity Constraint

For PTES and TTES plants $p \in \{\text{PTES, TTES}\}$:

$$\bar{c}h_p^{DH} \leq \bar{g}_p^{DH} \quad (55)$$

As only the generation has allocated costs, the charging capacity is expected to be set equal to the generation capacity by the model.

2.18.3 RES Generation Fixing Constraint

For new RES investment plants $p \in \mathcal{P}^{inv} \cap \mathcal{P}^{RES}$:

$$g_{p,t,s} = A_{p,t,s} \cdot \bar{g}_p \quad (56)$$

This forces RES plants to generate at maximum available capacity.

3 Model Characteristics

3.1 Model Type

This is a linear program (LP). The model is implemented in Python using the Pyomo optimization modeling framework [1, 5] and solved using Gurobi [4]. The model uses:

- Continuous variables for generation, storage, and flows
- Quadratic terms in the objective function (can be linearized)
- Multi-period optimization with hourly resolution
- Multi-scenario stochastic optimization with scenario weights

3.2 Temporal Resolution

- Hourly time steps ($t \in \mathcal{T}$)
- Weekly aggregation for certain constraints (EV, heat pumps, DSR)
- Daily aggregation for DSR balance
- Annual limits for fuel consumption

3.3 Spatial Coverage

- Multiple electricity nodes (European countries/regions)
- Transmission lines with NTC limits
- District heating nodes (city-level)
- No explicit network modeling (DC power flow not included)

3.4 Technology Coverage

Electricity: Hydro (reservoir, run-of-river, pumped storage), conventional (coal, gas, nuclear, oil), renewables (PV, wind onshore/offshore), batteries, hydrogen storage, EVs (V1G, V2G), demand-side response

District Heating: CHP plants, heat pumps, resistive heaters, thermal energy storage (PTES, TTES), biomass boilers, building thermal mass flexibility

4 Conclusion

This document provides a comprehensive mathematical description of the Future Energy Market (FEM) model. The formulation balances model complexity with computational tractability, enabling detailed analysis of future energy systems while maintaining reasonable solution times. The simplified notation employed in this document focuses on the essential mathematical structure, making the model accessible to researchers and practitioners in energy system modeling.

5 Acknowledgments

Data and Expertise: We thank the competence centre "HSLU - CC Thermal Energy Storage" for providing the expertise and heat data that enabled the implementation of the district heating sector in the FEM model (see [8]). To clarify, the provided heat data includes:

- heat demand time series (households and district heating),
- flexibility potentials (households and district heating), and
- heat potentials from natural resources.

Funding: The authors wish to acknowledge funding by the Swiss Federal Office of Energy's "Energy-Economics-Society" programme as part of the STORSUPPORT project (grant number SI/502888). Within this grant, the FEM model was substantially further developed.

References

- [1] Bynum, Michael L.; Hackebeil, Gabriel A.; Hart, William E.; Laird, Carl D.; Nicholson, Bethany L.; Sirola, John D.; Watson, Jean-Paul; Woodruff, David L. *Pyomo–Optimization Modeling in Python*. Third edition, Volume 67. Springer Science & Business Media, 2021.
- [2] Darudi, Ali. *The Future Electricity Market Model - FEM: Model Description*. EconStor Preprints 306396, ZBW - Leibniz Information Centre for Economics, 2024.
- [3] ENTSO-E & ENTSOG. *Methodology for ΔNTC Calculations*. March 2022. Available at: <https://eepublicdownloads.blob.core.windows.net/public-cdn-container/tyndp-documents/TYNDP2022/public/CBA-IG.pdf>.
- [4] Gurobi Optimization, LLC. *Gurobi Optimizer Reference Manual*. 2024. Available at: <https://www.gurobi.com>.
- [5] Hart, William E.; Watson, Jean-Paul; Woodruff, David L. Pyomo: Modeling and Solving Mathematical Programs in Python. *Mathematical Programming Computation*, 3(3):219–260, 2011.
- [6] Schlecht, Ingmar; Weigt, Hannes. Swissmod - A Model of the Swiss Electricity Market. June 6, 2014. Available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=2446807>.

-
- [7] Swiss Federal Office of Energy. *Energy Perspectives 2050+: Technical Report*. 2022. Available at: <https://www.bfe.admin.ch/bfe/de/home/politik/energieperspektiven-2050-plus.html>.
- [8] Schneeberger, Sarah; Meister, Curtis; Schuetz, Philipp. Estimating the heating energy demand of residential buildings in Switzerland using only public data. *Energy and Buildings*, Volume 347, Part B, 2025, 116371. ISSN 0378-7788. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2025.116371>.